

APPROACH TO COST-MODELLING FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL SPECTRUM MONITORING SYSTEMS

*Plossky A.,
Deputy Head of laboratory
Radio Research and Development Institute (NIIR), Moscow
Pavlyuk (Pavliouk) A.
Ph.D., Consultant JSC IRKOS, Moscow*

Abstract

This article proposes the approach to the cost-modelling for development of spectrum monitoring systems, including capital (CAPEX) and operational (OPEX) costs and staff considerations. This model could be implemented in cases of upgrading existing spectrum monitoring system or for creation of the new one. Proper cost-modelling allows countries to set the tight timelines for spectrum management system development projects to meet the short-term, mid-term and long-term goals.

Keywords: Spectrum management, spectrum monitoring, spectrum monitoring equipment and services, cost-modelling.

1. Introduction

Implementation of an efficient national spectrum monitoring system (NSMS), especially as it concerns monitoring network infrastructure, always relates to the significant number of issues which reflects in need of great investments. Different generations of equipment, existence of various vendors, interconnection issues, lack of experienced staff and non-systematic station-by-station approach on upgrading the NSMS – these issues are common for developing countries.

The main internationally-recognized source of information on development of NSMS is the Handbook on Spectrum Monitoring [1] of International Telecommunication Union (ITU), but unfortunately there is no comprehensive information on cost-modelling and proper consideration of economic aspects. At the same time, ITU-R Report SM.2012 on Economic aspects of spectrum management [2] contains a lot of useful materials on economic considerations but not in the relation to spectrum monitoring issues. In [3] authors provided cost-estimations of some NSMS elements but there is no information on supplementary CAPEX, and the OPEX is not considered at all. In the common situation of funding the NSMS development by limited finance resources of a national budget or even by the profit of a national telecommunication regulatory authority (NTRA), understanding of planning expenses for the different scenarios, options and terms is necessary to launch proper tenders [4]. Abovementioned analysis of previous publications shows the insufficiency of comprehensive cost-modelling materials in the field of the national spectrum management development. Below the approach to cost-modelling for the different scenarios of such development is described.

2. Scenarios for the development of national spectrum monitoring systems

The following three scenarios of NSMS development will be considered:

- short-term scenario;
- mid-term scenario;
- long-term scenario.

Short-term scenario

The initial scenario, which could be the end-point one in case of scarce of existing financial, human and

technical resources or in case of maturity of existing NSMS for about twenty years. Over the scenario which could be conducted in the short-term period (up to 2 years), two typical actions can be implemented:

- 1) System project.
- 2) Minor upgrading existing spectrum monitoring stations.

System project usually consists of three stages:

1) Initial assessment. At this stage NTRA itself or by invited experts conduct assessment of existing NSMS, including in-field testing and monitoring coverage evaluation using appropriate software.

2) Setting the goals for development of NSMS. At this stage NTRA itself or by invited experts sets the goals for NSMS considering available finance, human and technical resources.

3) Conducting the project. At this stage NTRA itself or by invited experts with the help of specific monitoring coverage software (for example, described in Annex 5 to ITU Handbook on Computer-aided Techniques for Spectrum Management (CAT) [5]) and using the internationally-recognized procedures, for example, for VHF-UHF frequency ranges [6], provides the necessary studies. They should also include the estimation of CAPEX and OPEX for the different timeframes of the project.

Considering the usual difficulties for developing countries to acquire new core equipment for NSMS, minor upgrades for existing monitoring stations may consist of:

- shifting existing monitoring stations for new places to provide better monitoring coverage;
- adjusting the heights of monitoring antennas for the same reason;
- installation of new stations (only if core equipment is already bought and interoperable with the existing one);
- improving engineering systems (conditioning, information exchange network, security, etc.).

These actions could be done after conducting abovementioned system project, which includes the monitoring coverage optimization by software calculations and in-field assessments.

Mid-term scenario

Possibly conducting together with or just after short-term scenario, this is the core one for undeveloped or absent NSMS. Over the scenario which could be performed in the mid-term period (2 to 5 years), there are two typical actions:

- 1) Acquiring and installing new monitoring stations for NSMS both fixed and mobile ones to cover major cities and economically attractive zones.
- 2) Upgrading the existing spectrum monitoring stations, for example, replacing non-operable monitoring equipment before depreciation period is over.

Long-term scenario

This scenario conducts over the period of 5-10 years and includes the following actions:

- 1) Further acquiring and installing new monitoring stations for NSMS such as fixed, mobile, transportable ones and handheld equipment to cover the major part or the whole territory of the country.
- 2) Replacing of outdated existing monitoring equipment whose depreciation period is over.

3. Cost-modelling for the development of the national spectrum monitoring systems

Considering the above-mentioned scenarios for the NSMS development, cost-modelling should be conducted upon the system project stages of the short-term scenario. Setting the right goals for NSMS development should be based on the proper estimation of project's cash-flow and sustainable cost-model. In this article, the reference cost-model for the NSMS development is outlined, so a lot of assumptions will be made. Below the algorithm of cost-modelling is traced.

Step 1. Estimation of CAPEX cost of new monitoring stations

By this stage NTRA or invited experts using the data on the costs (for example, acquired through a tender, see also [4]) estimates the average equipment cost of fixed and mobile monitoring stations and associated services. This estimation includes:

- core monitoring equipment and supplementary engineering systems (conditioning, information exchange network, security, etc.);
- related construction works, including installation and transportation of monitoring equipment,
- antenna masts and shelters installation;
- civil works, if necessary, including building construction and road laying, provision of water supply and sewerage;
- commissioning works including connection to broadband communication and electric networks;
- installation of security, alarm and lightning protection systems;
- checking, testing and tuning the hardware and software, including acceptance testing;
- warranty and after warranty services, etc.

This is the core expenses for mid-term and long-term scenarios, but in case of shifting the existing monitoring stations for new places, construction and commissioning work calculations for short-term scenario can be used.

Step 2. Estimation of cost of antenna masts

By this stage NTRA or invited experts using the data on the costs of metal constructions for the different heights of antenna and costs of foundation, including the costs of transportation and construction works estimates the reference configuration of antenna masts for existing fixed monitoring stations for CAPEX of any scenario and estimates the cost of shifting the existing monitoring stations for new places and increasing the heights of monitoring antennas if these actions considerably increase monitoring coverage of stations.

Step 3. Calculation of cost for short-term scenario

Considering the assumptions that short-term scenario actions will not imply the expanding the monitoring stuff and increasing the general maintenance cost, the system project and minor upgrades the existing spectrum monitoring stations require only CAPEX.

Step 4. Evaluation of needs in changing the number of existing monitoring staff

By this stage NTRA or invited experts using the data on the existing monitoring staff and statistics on the correlation between the total number of monitoring stations and the number of staff (for example, from [7]), estimates the OPEX related to the necessary expansion of different categories of monitoring staff for mid-term and long-term scenarios.

Step 5. Estimation of increase the OPEX for NSM

By this stage NTRA or invited experts using the data on OPEX for existing NSMS estimates the additional OPEX for mid-term and long-term scenarios, including depreciation deductions, maintenance fees, connection fees, electricity fees, rental costs and salaries of staff.

Step 6. Calculation of cost for mid-term and long-term scenarios

By this stage NTRA or invited experts using the data acquired at previous steps estimates the CAPEX and OPEX for mid-term and long-term scenarios.

Step 7. Additional calculations

Additional calculations could consist of the investment plans based on the year-by-year available finance resources, price adjustments on new financial inputs or changes in setting goals for the development of NSMS, etc.

4. Conclusion

As a reference model, it could be adjusted based on the complexity of NSMS development goals and available resources. Abovementioned approach for cost-modelling was successfully implemented by the authors in system projects on the NSMS development for one developing country. Average estimation for system project was about 50 000 USD, shifting one fixed monitoring station (to provide better monitoring coverage) was about 80 000 USD, increasing the antenna mast height for $H_a=60\text{m}$ (construction of the new antenna mast) was about 150 000 USD, expanding the network for one more new fixed monitoring station was about 300 000 USD as CAPEX and 25 000 USD as OPEX.

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АНАЛИЗ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЗАЗЕМЛЯЮЩИХ УСТРОЙСТВ СУДОВОГО ЭЛЕКТРООБОРУДОВАНИЯ

Есев А.И.

Дунайский институт Национального университета “Одесская морская академия”, старший преподаватель кафедры судовых энергетических установок и систем

ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF GROUNDING DEVICES SHIPS ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT

Yesyev A.

Danube Institute of the National University “Odessa Maritime Academy”, Senior Lecturer of the Department of Ship Power Plants and Systems

Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены основные аспекты использования заземляющих устройств судового электрооборудования. Рассмотрены вопросы повышения электробезопасности на морских судах и требования Международных морских классификационных обществ к защитным заземлениям. Приведены описания конструкции, принципа действия и эксплуатации устройств заземления. Выполнен анализ использования заземляющих устройств судового электрооборудования и с учетом этого даны дополнительные рекомендации по установке защитных заземляющих устройств.

Abstract

The article discusses the main aspects of the use of grounding devices for ship electrical equipment. The issues of improving electrical safety on ships and the requirements of the International Marine Classification Societies for protective grounding are considered. Descriptions of the design, principle of operation and operation of grounding devices are given. An analysis of the use of grounding devices of ship electrical equipment has been carried out and, taking this into account, additional recommendations have been given on the installation of protective grounding devices.

Ключевые слова: корпус судна, проводник, защитное заземление, площадь сечения, сопротивление, электротравма.

Keywords: ship hull, conductor, protective earth, cross-sectional area, resistance, electrical injury.

Технический прогресс на морском транспорте характеризуется увеличением энерговооруженности судов и насыщением их современными видами электрооборудования. Все это требует повышенного внимания к вопросам электробезопасности на флоте.

На современных судах весь судовой экипаж, а не только специалисты-электромеханики, связан с обслуживанием электрооборудования и различных электрических приборов. Поэтому в условиях плавания на морском судне электротравма возможна как в процессе эксплуатации электротехнического оборудования, так и при выполнении других работ

(в машинном отделении, на палубе, на камбузе, в прачечной, в танке, котле и т.д.). Для повышения безопасности труда на морских судах важно, чтобы каждый член экипажа, независимо от его специальности, хорошо ориентировался в вопросах электробезопасности.

Технический надзор за строящимися и эксплуатируемыми морскими судами осуществляет Международная ассоциация классификационных обществ, МАКО (англ. International Association of Classification Societies, IACS) - международное объединение классификационных обществ, ставящее